

PBO FABRIC REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE MANUFACTURED BY SOLUTION IMPREGNATION METHOD

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1. General Introduction

Fiber-reinforced plastic composites are becoming one of the most important lightweight materials, particularly in aircraft, F-1 cars, and the wind-energy industry, because of their high specific stiffness and strength, as well as their outstanding fatigue performance and high chemical resistance, and become irreplaceable nowadays. Depending on the polymers that used as the matrix, these materials can be classified into two categories, fiber reinforced thermosetting plastic (FRP) and fiber reinforced thermoplastic (FRTP). The FRTP have several advantages over those based on thermosetting plastic materials, including improved toughness and better recyclability as well as the possibility of a rapid processing cycle that does not involve a chemical reaction [1]. The commonly employed molding methods for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are injection and compression moldings, in which the discontinuous fibers are dispersed in the thermoplastic matrices as the reinforcement; hence the enhancement cannot be compared with that of continuous fibers. Be reinforced by continuous fibers the thermoplastic composites can be expected for superior mechanical properties.

The main problem in using the thermoplastic matrices for composites is the difficulty in impregnating the fibrous reinforcement with the higher viscosity resins (100-5000Pa·s) compared to thermosetting (typically less than 100Pa·s) [2,3]. As a result of high melt viscosity it requires significantly high processing temperature and pressure during fabrication, but thermoplastic matrices usually have a very high melting or softening temperature close to their degradation temperature, indicating that it is not successful to

reduce the viscosity by raising the processing temperature. This is the major drawback of thermoplastic composites which limited their properties and extensive applications.

For years, some methods have been developed for improving the impregnation of reinforcing fiber with thermoplastic matrices, which are [4,5] (1) film stacking method (2) plied matrix method (3) powder method (4) Co-woven method (5) Commingled yarn method. The schematic drawing of these methods were shown in figure 1. These efforts were made on the mixing approach of matrix and reinforcement to reduce the impregnation length which means the distance that the matrix resin must flow in order to complete the impregnation process to the required level under proper heat and pressure [6]. On the other hand, other efforts have been made on the approaches for reducing the viscosity of matrix in the impregnation process. Such as polymerization of monomers in situ [7], which is limited in the polymer matrix can be polymerized in situ, and a more fruitful variant of this approach is using a low molecular weight thermoplastic polymer and then increasing the molecular weight by chain extension after impregnation has taken place [8]. Also the methods of using solvent and plasticizer [9,10] are taking into account; the most important aspect to be remembered is that the solvent must be removed from the manufactured composite after impregnation.

Most of the methods mentioned above are working on the fiber bundles level, and the mixing and low viscosity methods all have beneficial effects on the impregnation process. But for the woven reinforcement fabrics having many interweaving points between warp and weft yarns redoubles the impregnation length of fiber bundles. It becomes much more difficult to acquire perfect impregnation.

According to the law of mixture, the final composite product mechanical properties are greatly influenced by the fiber volume fraction [11]. It is useful for transferring the properties of reinforcement to the integer composite with a high fiber volume fraction, thus, it is necessary to improve it as much as possible, in ideal condition, it is expected that the most volume in the composite is occupied by fiber, and the rest is matrix which forming good adhesion between the fibers. Therefore, it is considered that impregnation at low viscosity is much more preferable in manufacturing fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite.

For achieving better impregnation and higher fiber volume fraction, in this paper, a new vacuum assisted solution impregnation prepreg thermoplastic composite molding method was proposed, and the feasibility of this method was confirmed by the mechanical properties of the resultant composites. In this proposed method, the Poly (p-phenylenebenzobisoxazole) (PBO) fabric with plain weave was used as the reinforcement, to improve the bonding strength between the reinforcement fiber and the thermoplastic matrix the fabric was firstly treated by corona discharge surface treatment, then the treated fabric was impregnated by solution of thermoplastic under vacuum circumstance, after the volatilization of solvent the thermoplastic prepreg can be prepared for the further composite plate manufacture. The laminated prepreg sheets were hot pressed to prepare fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite, after the fiber fraction was calculated, the mechanical properties were investigated and compared with those of thermosetting composite reinforced by the same original fiber.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and composite manufacture

PBO fiber, a rigid-rod isotropic crystal polymer material, is one of the high performance synthetic fibers which display many excellent properties such as the high Young modulus, superior tensile strength and excellent thermal resistance [12-14] in comparison with the traditional polymeric materials. The PBO fiber can be used as reinforcement for advanced composites and has great potential applications in the fields of aeronautical and astronautical, military industry, general industry and other advanced domains [15]. The PBO reinforcing

fabric used in this paper is ZYLON® HM (High Modulus) supplied by TOYOBO co., LTD., with tensile strength and modulus of 5.8GPa and 270GPa respectively.

The thermoplastic matrix used in this study is crystalline co-polyester obtained from TOYOBO co., LTD., with the following main physical properties: glass transition temperature is 78°C, no established melting point but softening point at 185°C and a melt viscosity of 7000dPa·s at 250°C.

The NMP (N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, KANTO CHEMICAL CO., INC.) served as the solvent for preparing the impregnation solution of the thermoplastic matrix.

In order to achieve better impregnation, the crystalline co-polyester resin was dissolved in NMP using a hot-plate magnetic stirrer (Coring PC-420D) at different weight percentages (15, 20, 25, and 30 wt%) at 100 °C. The viscosity of the solution was measured using viscosity-measuring equipment (Brookfield Viscometer DV-I Prime), based on JIS K 7117-1 (plastic resins in the liquid state or as emulsions or dispersions; determination of apparent viscosity by the Brookfield Test Method) and compared with that of an epoxy resin.

PBO fabric is produced for clothing applications and has a chemically inert smooth surface and few oxygen-containing functional groups. The performance of a composite depends largely on the interfacial adhesion between the matrix and the reinforcement, which determines how stress is transferred from the polymer to the reinforcing fiber. It is therefore necessary to improve the adhesion properties using a fiber surface treatment [16-18]. In this work, a corona discharge (Corona Master PS-1M, Shinko Electric & Instrumentation Co., Ltd.) surface treatment was used as a chemical reactor to add polar bonds and hydrogen bonds to the fiber surface; the bonds most frequently encountered are C–O, C=O, C–O–O·, and C–OOH [19]. These bonds are promising for increasing the bonding strength between the PBO fibers and the thermoplastic matrix.

Next, the hand layup method was used for pre-impregnation of the reinforcing fabric with the matrix solution, which has a much lower viscosity than the melted resin. After hand layup pre-impregnation, the fabric was placed in a vacuum oven, and the temperature was increased from ambient temperature to 200 °C under vacuum over 2

h. During this process, the vacuum helped to achieve better impregnation and complete volatilization of the solvent NMP. The prepreg was obtained after returning to room temperature and atmospheric pressure, during which the thermoplastic resin froze to a rigid state.

During prepreg manufacture, to verify that the solvent was completely removed, the weight of the reinforcing fabric (w_F) and the weights before and after solvent evaporation (w_b and w_a , respectively) were measured. Then equation (1) was used to calculate the weight percentage (wt%) of the solution used in the experiment. By comparing the result with the weight percentage of a prepared solution, it could be determined whether or not the solvent was completely removed.

$$wt\% = \frac{w_a - w_F}{w_b - w_F} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

The prepreg sheet was then hot pressed (table-type test press, SA-302, Tester Sangyo Co., Ltd.) at 200°C and 0.26 MPa to tidy the surface and squeeze out excess resin before the next manufacturing step. This step is helpful for improving the fiber volume fraction in the final composite product.

In composites manufacture process prepreg sheets were laminated in the metallic molds (Fig. 3) with different thickness and hot pressed under the same pressure, temperature and pressure residence time, which were 7.8MPa, 200°C and 30min, after the process cycling, test samples with different fiber volume fraction were prepared. For tensile property comparison, the PBO fabric treated by corona discharge treatment reinforced epoxy resin (epoxy resin XNR 6815, harder XNH 6815, Nagase ChemteX Corporation) composite prepared by hand layup method was also put to tensile test.

2.3 Bonding and tensile tests

In the bonding tests, the prepreg was arranged according to the diagram in Fig. 4. After hot pressing for 30 min at a pressure of 6.97 MPa, a bonding test was performed using a Shimadzu Autograph at a drawing velocity of 10 mm/min. The average bonding strength was calculated from at least five specimens. The bonding strength of a

PBO-fiber-reinforced epoxy resin was also investigated for comparison.

Samples were cut from the fiber-reinforced composites and tensile experiments were performed using a Shimadzu Autograph, based on JIS K 7054 (testing method for tensile properties of glass-fiber-reinforced plastic). The size of the test sample is shown in Fig. 5, and the drawing velocity was 1 mm/min. Two strain gages (KFG-5-120-C1-11L1M2R, Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co., Ltd.) were longitudinally bonded at the center of both sides of each test specimen to get the actual tensile modulus. An average was taken from at least five specimens of each sample.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Bonding property

In order to find out the influence of corona discharge treatment on bonding property, the fabric treated for 0s, 5s, 10s, 15s and 20s (the length of the fabric is 20cm) reinforced composites (the matrix mass fraction in the solution is 25%) were investigated, the bonding experiment results are shown in fig. 6. In the graph, the bonding strength does change with the treatment time, so the treatment time was decided to 10s, which has the best treatment effect shown in the experiment results.

The bonding strength of fabric with the same treated time (10s) impregnated by different matrix (the thermoplastic solutions with different matrix mass fraction of 15%, 20%, 25% and 30% and epoxy) were studied to find out the influence of matrix mass fraction on the bonding property. The testing results are shown in fig. 7.

When the resin mass fraction is 30wt%, under the vacuum assistance in prepreg manufacture, the bonding strength was increased about 35%. The vacuum assistance is not only conducive in assisting impregnation but also in solvent volatilization. Because of the existing pressure difference, the left void in the fabric after hand layup pre-impregnation was eliminated, and the matrix will be filled in. In addition, the solvent was gasified during the temperature increase from ambient temperature to 200°C and the gaseous solvent was immediately

removed from the fabric lamina without leaving any void in the fabric lamina.

Table 1 shows the weights measured during the prepreg manufacture and the calculated solution weight percentages; these results confirmed that there was no residual solvent left in the prepreg. It is therefore unnecessary to worry about the negative impact of the residual solvent on the final composites properties.

Considering the influence of resin mass fraction, it has the best bonding property at 20wt% and 25wt% which is similar to that of epoxy. From the viscosity curve of the matrix in Fig.8, it is because the solutions (20wt% and 25wt%) have similar viscosity with epoxy and proper amount of matrix, which are helpful for getting perfect impregnation. When the mass fraction is 15wt%, it is easy for impregnation but the amount of matrix is too low that leave some void between the fiber laminations leading to weak bond among the fiber laminas, which made the sample has the worst bonding property; when the mass fraction is 30wt%, the viscosity is higher than others (15wt%, 20wt% and 25wt%), the impregnation is not as good as 20wt% and 25wt%, so the bonding strength is lower even the amount of resin is the highest. In the matrix solution, the solution viscosity and amount of resin are contrary parameters which both have strong effects on the final product, in this paper, from the results of bonding test, the mass fraction equilibrium points are at 20wt% and 25wt%. In tensile test, the prepreg produced by 25wt% matrix solution impregnating PBO fabric was prepared for making composite plate.

3.2 Tensile properties

Fig. 9 shows a representative tensile stress-strain curve of PBO reinforced thermoplastic composite with a fiber volume fraction of 61%. The sample was broken at the mark “×” and the tensile strength was taken from this point. The gradient of the dashed line in the graph is considered as the tensile modulus of the test sample. The average tensile strength and tensile modulus were shown in fig. 10.

In ZFRTP both the tensile strength and tensile modulus are improved with the increased fiber volume fraction. In ZFRP the fiber volume fraction

is a bit lower than that of ZFRTP which is depend on manufacture condition. By calculation, the tensile strength of ZFRTP and ZFRP is similar, and ZFRP has a higher tensile modulus than ZFRTP if the fiber volume fractions are the same. In addition, the resin may have strong effect on the tensile modulus.

By investigating the tensile properties of PBO fiber reinforced both thermoplastic and thermosetting plastic, they have the similar tensile properties which indicated that the molding method of using thermoplastic resin solution and vacuum assisted impregnation in the manufacture of thermoplastic composite is available.

4. Conclusion

Vacuum-assisted solution impregnation prepreg thermoplastic composite molding, to improve the fiber volume fractions in FRTP composites, was investigated. After pre-impregnation of the reinforcing fibers with thermoplastic resin solution, a vacuum was employed for further impregnation and solvent volatilization in the prepreg manufacturing process. The treatment time for the fabric and the solution conditions were determined (10s/20 cm and 25 wt%, respectively) based on bonding tests. Under the determined manufacturing conditions, the fiber volume fraction in the thermoplastic composite material reached 60%, which is similar to those of laboratory-produced fiber-reinforced thermosetting composites. The tensile strength and tensile modulus were improved to levels similar to those of PFRP after the fiber volume fraction of PFRTP was improved. Tensile tests and comparisons confirmed the effectiveness of vacuum-assisted solution impregnation. The feasibility of the proposed method was confirmed, and its application is promising in the manufacture of carbon- or glass-fiber-reinforced thermoplastics when the reinforcing materials are in the form of fabric.

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Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of conventional fabrication methods of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite materials: (1) Film stacking method; (2) Plied matrix method; (3) Powder method; (4) Co-Woven method and (5) Commingled yarn method.

Fig. 2 Diagram of metallic mold used in hot press process.

Fig. 4 Diagram of tensile test sample.

Fig. 3 Diagram of bonding test sample.

Fig. 5 Influence of corona discharge treatment time on the bonding strength.

Fig. 6 Influence of resin on the bonding strength.

Fig. 7 Viscosity curve of the matrix.

Fig. 8 Comparison of tensile properties.

Table 1. Calculated solution weight percentage when the prepared solution weight percentage is 25%.

	w_F (g)	w_a (g)	w_b (g)	wt%
1	137	151	192	25.45%
2	139	151	187	25.00%
3	138	151	189	25.49%